

IHI Project ID - SYNTHIA

Synthetic Data Generation
Framework for Integrated
Validation

WP10

D10.1-2024

Project communication, dissemination and engagement materials

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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	15/11/2024	1 st version for review
V0.2	19/11/2024	PMO revision
V0.3	22/11/2024	SC revision
V0.4	29/11/2024	Final version

Executive Summary

The SYNTHIA communication plan emphasizes a versatile, agile, and cohesive approach to ensure broad yet targeted outreach to all relevant stakeholder groups. This strategy prioritizes raising awareness by clearly presenting the project's key aspects and benefits to diverse audiences, including end users.

Easily interpretable, recognizable, and visually engaging materials will be developed to ensure that SYNTHIA's concepts and value propositions are quickly understood by a broad audience, fostering interest and support for the project's objectives.

Tailored content will be crafted for specialized groups (Table A) to cultivate and maintain an active stakeholder ecosystem. Additionally, insights from interviews with partners, the project scope broken down in tasks and deliverables, case studies, and reports will be shared through SYNTHIA's communication channels, reinforcing ongoing engagement and supporting the growth of an informed and invested community around synthetic data generation.

Tailored interaction activities will be set up for data and disease specific communities. These activities entail F2F and online participation in selected conferences and meetings. Initiating SYNTHIA webinars, workshops and training programs will be part of the plan. The scale and significance of the SYNTHIA communication, engagement and dissemination of project results, as well as policy engagement and training will be further detailed in D10.05 'Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation of Results, including Communication Activities,' which is scheduled for delivery in month 6.

This strategy will serve as the foundation for all SYNTHIA communications and will be periodically updated during the project's lifetime

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1 Communication objectives and strategy

For the IHI SYNTHIA project, the communication strategy focuses on positioning SYNTHIA as a benchmark synthetic data platform in European biomedical research. It aims to build a strong ecosystem that fosters collaboration and innovation while ensuring the project delivers lasting impact through effective outreach and stakeholder engagement. The following actions outline how these objectives will be achieved:

- **Build awareness and interest:** Effectively communicate SYNTHIA's goals and its mission to advance synthetic data generation, emphasizing its potential to transform personalized medicine. Highlight the innovative, validated tools and methods for synthetic data generation (SDG) that SYNTHIA will develop, underscoring their relevance and impact for a broad audience.
- **Drive Engagement:**
Contribute to the cohesion of public and private entities, sharing insights, good practices and evidence of the value from Synthetic Data. This community will also surface new requirements and new opportunities for Synthetic Data.
Establish and nurture relationships with key stakeholders (HTA, regulators, public health agencies, patient associations and policymakers) for advancement on the appropriate use of Synthetic Data and acceptability in evidence-based decision-making.
- **Highlight impact:** Illustrate SYNTHIA's significance by explaining the challenges it addresses, the methodologies it uses, and the advancements it seeks to bring to research and innovation. Showcase how SYNTHIA's synthetic data approach can accelerate research, improve data accessibility, and enable more efficient and ethical innovations across healthcare and life sciences and in particular for the 6 defined use cases.
- **Disseminate knowledge and results:** Actively share SYNTHIA's findings, methodologies, and project results. Facilitate knowledge transfer to maximize the project's reach, impact, and potential for applications. Ensure a wide outreach of the project outcomes.
- **Promote transparency:** Ensure SYNTHIA's processes, findings, and outcomes are communicated openly and accessibly. Provide clear, understandable updates to build trust and maintain credibility among all stakeholders.

2 Communication focus and policy group

The SYNTHIA communication focus and policy group plays a crucial role in shaping the project's communication strategy. Acting as a sounding board, it provides valuable insights into stakeholder preferences, expectations, and needs, enabling the development of a more effective and targeted communication approach. The group leverages diverse expertise, backgrounds, cultures, and networks to enrich the strategy.

Its envisioned members include representatives from SYNTHIA partners, spanning academia, industry, data science, patient advocacy, disease-specific medical associations, regulatory and ethical fields, policy makers and HTA agencies and communication experts. This diversity ensures the group can effectively engage with a wide range of audiences and identify the most impactful communication channels and platforms. Additionally, their input will guide the communication team in selecting topics that resonate with target audiences.

To maintain relevance and flexibility, the focus and policy group can expand by inviting additional experts for specific campaigns or initiatives.

3 Stakeholders and target audiences

SYNTHIA engages a diverse set of stakeholders and target audiences to achieve its mission of leveraging synthetic data to drive advancements in personalized medicine. Below is an overview of the key stakeholders and target audiences:

Table A: Overview SYNTHIA stakeholders and target audiences

I. Clinicians and physicians	Healthcare professionals, including physicians and clinicians at academic institutions, involved in research, innovation, and the practical application of personalized medicine.
II. Researchers and Data Scientists	Experts and institutions focused on data analysis, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and advanced biomedical research.
III. Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pharmaceutical Companies: Professionals involved in drug discovery, development, and clinical trials. • Medical Device Manufacturers: Engineers, designers, and developers of medical technologies. • Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and Innovators: Start-ups and companies contributing cutting-edge solutions to synthetic data and healthcare innovation.
IV. Patient advocacy groups & patients	Organizations and individuals representing patient interests, ensuring inclusivity and ethical considerations in synthetic data applications.
V. Regulators and Policymakers	Government bodies, regulatory authorities, health technology assessment (HTA) organizations, and policymakers responsible for establishing guidelines, policies, and standards related to synthetic data.
VI. Associations and groups	Medical associations, industry associations, scientific and technology working groups
VII. Related IHI and Horizon Europe projects as well as related global initiatives	IHI and EU funded projects – currently running and potentially new - focussed on big data, RWD, RWE, AI, machine learning and SD

4 Key Messages

Key communication messages for SYNTHIA will focus on the goals, innovations, impact, and the benefits of SD generation in personalized medicine. Eight themes that can be adapted in the communication toolkit are:

4.1 Advancing Personalized Medicine with Synthetic Data

- Message: SYNTHIA is revolutionizing personalized medicine by developing innovative methods for generating synthetic data, which could enable more precise and effective treatments tailored to individual patients.
- Why it matters: Personalized medicine holds the potential to transform healthcare by providing targeted therapies based on a patient's genetic profile, medical history, and other personal factors. SYNTHIA's work in sd generation enhances the ability to simulate and test these personalized treatments more efficiently.

4.2. Enhancing Data Accessibility and Privacy

- Message: SYNTHIA is creating validated tools and methodologies for SD generation that allow researchers and healthcare providers to access high-quality data while ensuring patient privacy and confidentiality.
- Why it matters: SD can replicate real-world data without exposing sensitive personal information, addressing privacy concerns in medical research and accelerating the pace of scientific discovery.

4.3 Supporting More Efficient and Ethical Innovation

- Message: By using SD, SYNTHIA helps speed up research and innovation processes, reducing the need for time-consuming real-world data collection, while maintaining high ethical standards in data use.
- Why it matters: Faster and more efficient innovation in healthcare, without compromising ethical standards, can lead to quicker advancements in treatments and medical solutions, benefiting patients and healthcare systems worldwide.

4.4 A Collaborative Effort for Better Outcomes

- Message: SYNTHIA is a collaborative project that brings together experts from diverse fields, including data science, healthcare, and policy, to encourage that SD technologies are integrated into healthcare systems to improve patient outcomes.
- Why it matters: The success of SYNTHIA relies on the expertise of various stakeholders, ensuring that solutions are both scientifically robust and practical for real-world healthcare settings.

4.5. Boosting Research Capabilities

- Message: SYNTHIA's SDG methods provide researchers with more data to work with, allowing them to run simulations, model new treatments, and test hypotheses without the constraints of real-world data limitations.
- Why it matters: Access to high-quality synthetic data allows researchers to explore more possibilities and reduce the time of testing new medical theories, which can ultimately lead to faster medical breakthroughs.

4.6. Transforming Healthcare with Innovative Technologies

- Message: SYNTHIA is at the forefront of transforming healthcare through the use of cutting-edge technologies such as synthetic data, artificial intelligence, and machine learning to accelerate innovation in medical treatments.
- Why it matters: With the rapid advancements in technology, SYNTHIA is positioning itself as enabler to reshaping how healthcare systems could approach diagnosis, treatment, and prevention in the future.

4.7 Creating a Trusted, Ethical Framework for SD

- Message: SYNTHIA is committed to developing a trusted, ethical framework for SDG, ensuring that its applications in healthcare are safe, transparent, and compliant with regulatory standards.
- Why it matters: Trust and ethics are essential for the widespread adoption of synthetic data in healthcare. SYNTHIA’s work ensures that the development and use of synthetic data uphold the highest ethical standards, fostering confidence among stakeholders.

4.8 Paving the Way for Future Health Innovations

- Message: SYNTHIA is laying the groundwork for future breakthroughs in healthcare by providing the infrastructure and methodologies to support advanced research in areas like genomics, drug development, and disease prevention.
- Why it matters: The foundation that SYNTHIA builds with synthetic data technology is not only addressing current challenges but also preparing the healthcare industry for the next generation of medical advances.

These key communication messages highlight the value of SYNTHIA’s work, its potential to transform personalized medicine, and the broader implications for healthcare innovation, data privacy, and research efficiency. Tailoring the key messages to the different stakeholders and target audiences will take place with the input of the SYNTHIA Communication Focus Group. Input for the tailored message is provided in the table below.

Table B: Overview of the SYNTHIA target audiences and their keymessages

I.Clinicians and physicians	Synthetic patient data resulting in new synthetic data-driven analytic tools facilitates clinical decision-making to develop personalized treatment strategies.
II.Researchers and Data Scientists	Access to enhanced SDG methods and extensive synthetic patient records offers researchers and scientists unprecedented data resources, potentially accelerating advancements in medical research.
III.Industry	Synthetic patient populations can open up possibilities for drug development and trials. Synthetic data will empower manufacturers to achieve more accurate and personalized products, with faster time to market.
IV.Patient advocacy groups & patients	New synthetic data-driven analytic tools will offer new and more personalized treatments.
V.Regulators and Policymakers	SD may be used to understand its potential implications for policy formulation related to health data privacy, security, ethical use.
VI.Associations and groups	Above mentioned benefits depending on the specific association/group.
VII.Related IHI and Horizon Europe projects as well as related global initiatives	Above mentioned benefits points depending on the specific project.

5 Communication, engagement and dissemination activities

To ensure the SYNTHIA project's objectives and progress are easily recognizable to a broad professional audience, visually engaging and professional materials will be developed. These materials will not only generate interest in the project, its team, and its outcomes but also support the building and maintenance of a connected and engaged stakeholder community. Tailored content will be crafted to meet the needs of different audiences, fostering ongoing engagement. Additionally, insights drawn from project deliverables, partner interviews, expert perspectives, and case studies will be shared through SYNTHIA's communication channels to deepen interaction and interest.

5.1 Visual identity

Consistent branding will contribute to recognition, effective communication and building trust and engagement with stakeholders. The SYNTHIA communications team already created a strong visual Identity ensuring a solid foundation for future outreach and communication effort.

This is an example of the SYNTHIA logo:

- in its full form: acronym, full name and icon

- in shortened form: acronym and icon

- only the icon:

The communication team has already developed the first version of the SYNTHIA brand book. A brand book is essential for ensuring consistency, recognition, and professionalism in all the SYNTHIA communication and outreach activities. It gives a quick overview of how SYNTHIA presents itself visually right from the start enabling recognizability and impact during the life cycle of the project. The communication team will make an effort, considering the multiple stakeholders involved in the SYNTHIA community, that all presentations and materials are aligned with SYNTHIA's identity. Annex 1 of D10.1 presents edition 1.0 of the SYNTHIA brand book.

As SYNTHIA evolves, the communication will grow and the developed house style will provide strong foundation for scaling communication efforts without deviating from the core identity. Included in the brand book are the logo, typography, color palette and imagery. In the near future, items such as standard layouts for presentations, reports, posters, social media posts etc. will be added.

5.2 Short profile text

In all communication, engagement, dissemination, policy and training activities SYNTHIA will be introduced in a consistent way by making use of a standard text. The text version of this introduction is as follow:

- The SYNTHIA project, a groundbreaking public-private partnership set to revolutionize the field of personalized medicine by harnessing the power of synthetic data. As the first IHI project to tackle the critical need for privacy-preserving data solutions in healthcare, SYNTHIA aims to propel research and innovation to new heights, ensuring that patients receive the best possible care while safeguarding their personal information.
- SYNTHIA is a multidisciplinary collaboration of 34 consortium partners - SDG developers, FAIR data experts, clinical researchers, developers of therapies and data-based tools, legal experts, socio-economic analysts, regulatory, policy advocacy, and communication experts - that will provide a 360° vision on how to advance healthcare applications through SD use.
- Synthetic data, which are artificially generated to mimic real patient data, present a solution to many of the challenges faced in health research today. These data allow researchers to overcome the limitations of access to high-quality, real-world datasets and address growing concerns about patient privacy. However, questions have lingered about the quality and applicability of synthetic datasets, especially in diverse and complex scenarios. SYNTHIA is addressing these challenges head-on by developing validated tools and methods for SDG across various data types, including laboratory results, clinical notes, genomics and imaging. By focusing on six specific diseases the project will demonstrate the utility of synthetic data in advancing personalized medicine: Lung cancer, Breast cancer, Multiple myeloma, Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma, Alzheimer's disease and Type 2 diabetes.

Added to this text profile will be the standard text for acknowledgement of IHI support.

5.2 Acknowledgement of IHI support

In all communication, engagement, dissemination, policy and training activities the IHI support will be acknowledged as follows:

This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, Europa Bio, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe and DNV. The UK consortium partner, The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) is supported by UKRI Grant No 10132181.

Moreover, once the State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI) funds the Associated Partner #29 CHUV the following will be added to the acknowledgement: "The Swiss consortium partner, the Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois (CHUV) is supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation Ref No. tbd".

5.3 The SYNTHIA communication toolkit

The SYNTHIA project’s communication, engagement, and dissemination activities are designed to maximize its impact and relevance throughout its lifecycle. These efforts are strategically planned to raise awareness about SD and to foster engagement with the project’s objectives, anticipated impact, and innovative visions for applying SD. By understanding the needs, concerns, and objectives of stakeholders in healthcare, pharmaceuticals, and MedTech, SYNTHIA aims to demystify SD, highlight its potential, and address associated ethical considerations.

Dissemination efforts will share project results widely, extending the reach of SD insights, promoting knowledge exchange, and encouraging collaboration. Policy engagement activities will leverage project insights to influence ethical frameworks and regulatory standards, ensuring alignment with societal and industry needs. Training initiatives will empower current and potential users with the skills and knowledge to adopt the tools and methods developed by the project.

These activities will follow a coherent theme and creative concept, executed across various communication channels with content written and spoken in English.

The communication toolkit as described in table C is a collection of resources and materials designed to support and streamline communication activities for a specific project, campaign, or initiative. The SYNTHIA tactics and activities as described below are geared to help shaping a landscape where SD fuels responsible and impactful decision-making by the health care and MedTech professionals in the six defined disease areas.

Table C: Overview of the SYNTHIA communication toolkit

Audiences	Tactics	Activities, materials and channels
All target audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide general SYNTHIA information and general project updates • Invite for presentations, lectures, sessions and meetings • Create clear and inspiring content • Use consistent and strong branding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Quarterly newsletter • Social media posts – <i>See examples in Annex 2</i> • Consortium partner and funder websites, newsletters and internal channels • Power Point decks – <i>See example in Annex 3</i> • Videos – <i>See recordings per September 2024 in Annex 4</i> • Infographics – <i>See example in Annex 5</i> • Quote cards – <i>See example in Annex 6</i> • Flyers and banners – <i>See example in Annex 7</i> • Podcasts • Press release – <i>See example in Annex 8</i>
I. Clinicians and physicians II. Researchers and Data Scientists III. Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide dedicated (disease specific) content about SD and about specific SYNTHIA activities, progress and results • Provide onboarding and informative kits • Approach personally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Special page(s) at the project website • (Free) editorials in journals and online platforms • Scientific publications in clinical, methodological and multidisciplinary journals • Selected conferences and events • Training webinars • Emailing
IV. Patient advocacy groups & patients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide dedicated (disease specific) content in lay-man terms • Invite for specific sessions and meetings • Approach personally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Special page(s) at the project website • Social media posts • Dedicated conferences sessions • Campaigns planned by the patient advocacy groups and patients in relation to disease specific awareness days
V. Regulators and Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide dedicated content • Provide report/white paper • Specific sessions and meetings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicated meetings • Emailing
VI. Associations and groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide communication and collaboration kits • Approach personally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Websites, newsletters, social media and selected conferences from and campaigns planned by associations and groups
VII. Related IHI and Horizon Europe projects as well as related global initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide communication and collaboration kits • Approach personally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Websites, newsletters, social media and selected conferences from and campaigns planned related IHI and Horizon Europe projects and global initiatives

For internal community engagement a dedicated SharePoint will be developed. In addition to the annual general assembly (GAM), the internal community will be offered (optional) informal virtual meet ups to foster the consortium partner relations. *See example in Annex 9.*

SYNTHIA materials and public deliverables will be hosted on Zenodo, the open repository for EU-funded research outputs from Horizon Europe. Access to Zenodo will be integrated into the SYNTHIA website, ensuring easy availability for stakeholders and the broader audience.

To maximize outreach and engagement, the SYNTHIA communication team will collaborate closely with consortium partners. These partners bring established networks, trusted relationships, and a variety of communication platforms that can significantly amplify the reach and impact of SYNTHIA’s messages. Additionally, many consortium members are actively involved in related IHI and Horizon Europe projects, creating opportunities for cross-promotion and synergy.

By coordinating with the communication contacts of consortium partners, the SYNTHIA team aims to leverage their social media accounts, newsletters, and event networks. This collaborative effort will also extend to SYNTHIA’s funder and supporting organizations, including COCIR, MedTech Europe, and EuropaBio, enabling broader visibility and deeper integration into relevant communities.

This strategy not only enhances the visibility of SYNTHIA but also reinforces a unified identity and collective impact for the project.

SYNTHIA’s external online channels play a vital role in ensuring the project’s visibility, accessibility, and impact across diverse audiences. These platforms serve as key tools for sharing updates, engaging stakeholders, and disseminating public deliverables. A comprehensive overview of these channels, including their specific purposes and target audiences, can be found in Table D.

Table D: Overview of the SYNTHIS External online channels

Medium	Url or name	Link
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website 	www.ih-synthia.eu	www.ih-synthia.eu
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LinkedIn 	IHI-SYNTHIA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ih-synthia
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X 	@IHI_SYNTHIA Note: depending on the current developments concerning the performance of X, the communication team may decide to switch to Bluesky. The account is already set up with the following name: @ih-synthia.bsky.social	https://x.com/IHI_SYNTHIA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> YouTube 	ih-synthia	https://www.youtube.com/@ih_synthia
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zenodo (login required) 	IHI-SYNTHIA	https://zenodo.org/ (Not installed yet)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Podbean (login required) 	IHI-SYNTHIA	https://www.podbean.com/user-K1RjWYAfpu

6 Communication collaboration

The SYNTHIA communication teams will serve as the central point of contact for internal and external communication, dissemination and engagement activities. By fostering collaboration with both internal partners and external stakeholders, SYNTHIA can enhance its visibility while leveraging complementary resources and networks to amplify its impact.

6.1 Internal collaboration

The communication team will maintain in close contact with all WP leaders, use case leads and specific project teams to stay informed and to keep track of new developments, decisions and results. The internal collaboration will also lead to insights across all aspects of the project guiding the content development for the various communication channels. Through this cross-disciplinary engagement, the communication team aims to create a more cohesive and unified message about the project's overall impact, which can be adopted by SYNTHIA partners in their own outreach efforts. This narrative will support partners in integrating SYNTHIA's messaging into their own outreach efforts, strengthening the project's overall impact. Internal communication efforts will be closely coordinated with the SYNTHIA project management organization to ensure alignment and efficiency.

6.2 External collaboration

Building relationships with stakeholders mentioned in Table A allows SYNTHIA to boost its outreach and ensure that the project goals and results are communicated to a wider audience. Also, the collaboration with related IHI projects and Horizon Europe projects is of utmost importance to align communications, as these projects may be working on similar challenges related to SD.

By coordinating with projects addressing similar challenges in SD, SYNTHIA aims to prevent fragmentation within the field, promote a unified approach, and accelerate the adoption of SD solutions across healthcare and related industries.

7 Scientific and technical publications

The communication team in close collaboration with the project management organization will guide SYNTHIA partners in disseminating results via publications. The purpose of disseminating via publications has several key purposes such as:

- Ensuring that key findings openly distributed to data science and disease specific communities.
- Ensuring continued interest and awareness about SDG and what this means for health care in general and for the personalized approach of treatment in the 6 defined diseases.
- Sharing experience, processes, and analyses approaches with other researchers, consortia and projects.

The SYNTHIA project teams have the intention to publish and contribute to peer-reviewed publications in top scientific journals. A first overview of targeted journals is listed in [Table E](#). By further alignment with SYNTHIA partners possible additional journals can be identified.

Table E: Overview envisioned journals for publication

Journal	Url	Impact factor	Publisher
• Nature machine intelligence	https://www.nature.com/natmachintell/ http://www.ihl-synthia.eu/	18.8	Springer Nature
• NPJ Digital Medicine	https://www.nature.com/npjdigitalmed/	12.4	Springer Nature
• IEEE Transactions on neural networks and learning systems	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=5962385	10.2	IEEE
• IEEE Journal of biomedical and health informatics	https://www.embs.org/ibhi/	6.7	IEEE EMBS
• Artificial intelligence in medicine	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/artificial-intelligence-in-medicine	6.1	Elseviers ScienceDirect
• Computer methods and programs in biomedicine	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/computer-methods-and-programs-in-biomedicine	4.9	Elseviers Science Direct
• Lancet digital health	https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landig/home	23.8	Elsevier
• Value in health	https://www.valueinhealthjournal.com/	4.9	ISPOR

In addition, the communication team will encourage the SYNTHIA project teams to make us of the platforms offered by the European Union such as:

- The Open research Europe platform: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>
- The Horizon results platform: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

The potential for journals for publication in the SYNTHIA defined 6 diseases still has to be further investigated.

Annex 1 - SYNTHIA Brand book edition 1.0

See separate PDF for all pages.

SYNTHIA Brand Book

Contact for all SYNTHIA communications
and dissemination, including artwork:

Ellen [P.B.] de Waal
e.dewaal@matical.com | +31 654 711703

Primary Logo

Primary Logo

“

Our logo blends a DNA-like strand with digital dots, forming a subtle “S” to signify the fusion of real world and synthetic data. The design represents the bridge between the need for comprehensive patient data and the challenges associated with accessing real patient data. With its vibrant colors the logo encapsulates continuity, innovation, future of data and technology.

Primary Logo

Primary
Logo with tagline

Vertical

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

*Primary
Logo with tagline*

Horizontal

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

Founders logo set

Always use together with the project text and a white background. If there is a dark background, the logo set should be placed on a white stripe at the bottom of the layout, with the stripe's top-right side curving upward.

This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, Europa Bío, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe and DNV.

Logo rules

Logo rules

Typography & Color

Typography & Colors

Primary

Plus Jakarta Sans

Nam fuga. Et et enimill essitatiis
dolorumet autem fugias alic tem il
idellor ehentur. Quisci bera volupta
vel et. Minullab orporrore magnim.

Secondary

Calibri

Nam fuga. Et et enimill essitatiis
dolorumet autem fugias alic tem
il idellor ehentur. Quisci bera
volupta vel et. Minullab orporrore
magnim.

Brand imagery

Brand imagery

Dark theme

Primary

Diseases

General

Brand imagery

Light theme

Primary

Diseases

General

Brand in action

Brand in action

Mock-ups to give you some idea.

Brand in action

Brand in action

This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, Europa Bío, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe and DNV.

[@IHI_SYNTHIA x.com/IHI_SYNTHIA](https://x.com/IHI_SYNTHIA)

www.linkedin.com/company/ihj-synthia

www.youtube.com/@ihj_synthia

www.ihj-synthia.eu

contact@ihj-synthia.eu
(for external communications purposes)

Annex 2 – Some examples social media posts

See separate PDF for more posts.

IHI-SYNTHIA
642 followers
2mo · 🌐

A big hello to the world by all SYNTHIA consortium partners, just finishing the 1st day of the Kick-off meeting at **Medical Research Institute La Fe (IIS La Fe)**

SYNTHIA stands for **#SyntheticData** generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI hashtag **#Healthcare** applications. A pioneering multidisciplinary collaboration of 32 consortium partners – synthetic data generation (SDG) developers, FAIR data experts, clinical researchers, developers of therapies and data-based tools, legal experts, socio-economic analysts, regulatory, policy advocacy, and communication experts - that will provide a 360° vision on how to advance healthcare applications through synthetic data (SD) use.

SYNTHIA is funded by the **Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)** under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA - European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations, EuropaBio - the European Association for Bioindustries, MedTech Europe, Vaccines Europe and DNV. Supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program and industry leaders such as COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe, Vaccines Europe, and DNV, SYNTHIA is dedicated to advancing synthetic data generation for healthcare applications, ensuring that data-driven innovations can safely and effectively transform patient care.

#hematology #MMSM #DLBCL #oncology #lungcancer #breastcancer #Alzheimers #diabetes

#EURsearch #EUInnovation #HealthResearch #DataGeneration #DataScience #DataInnovation #AIinHealthcare #DigitalHealth #HealthData #PublicPrivatePartnership #PersonalizedMedicine

IHI-SYNTHIA
642 followers
2w · 🌐

#SyntheticData, artificially generated to mimic real patient data, presents a solution to many of the challenges faced in **#Health** **#research** today. These data allow researchers to overcome the limitations of access to high-quality, real-world datasets and address growing concerns about patient privacy. Questions have lingered about the quality and applicability of synthetic datasets, especially in diverse and complex scenarios.

>>>>>

SYNTHIA will address these challenges head-on by developing validated tools and methods for **#syntheticdatageneration** (SDG) across various data types, including laboratory results, clinical notes, genomics and imaging.

>>>>>

Sign up for our newsletter, mail to: contact@ihi-synthia.eu

#SyntheticData #DataGeneration #PrecisionMedicine -> funded by Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)

synthia

- Identify requirements for SD with SYNTHIA clinical use cases
- Develop SDG methods, tools & access to RD
- Establish a framework for SD evaluation, ensuring privacy, quality and bias mitigation
- Validation of SD for various use cases
- Provide access to SD & SDG methods
- Build a community through public-private cohesion and strong communication

Objectives

IHI-SYNTHIA
642 followers
6d · 🌐

SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT:
Aleksandar Batic from DNV, Norway, shares his vision for the future of **#SyntheticData**.

"Our wish is basically to transition from synthetic data as hype into synthetic data becoming a reality, becoming a standard tool in the toolbox for researchers. We hope that Europe can be a preferred place to drive this development that will evolve around personalized medicine". DNV is an independent expert in assurance and risk management. Listen to his SYNTHIA message.

#SYNTHIA #SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #PublicPrivatePartnership #CollaborativeResearch #HealthData #FutureOfMedicine #AIinHealthcare #DigitalHealth #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURsearch
Funded by the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)

SYNTHIA
@IHI_SYNTHIA

#SyntheticData are essential for warranting data privacy and simultaneously, advancing **#PrecisionMedicine**, accelerating patients' access to more effective drugs while preserving the sustainability of EU healthcare systems. With a focus on 6 impactful diseases—**#lungcancer**, **#breastcancer**, **#MMSM** (multiple myeloma), **#DLBCL** (Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma), **#Alzheimers**, and **#Type2diabetes**—we will develop, disease-specific SDG solutions.

#SYNTHIA #SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #HealthcareInnovation #PersonalizedMedicine #PersonalizedHealthcare #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURsearch

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Disease Focus

- Lung Cancer
- Multiple Myeloma
- Glioblastoma & Glioma
- Breast Cancer
- DLBCL
- Type 2 Diabetes

SYNTHIA
@IHI_SYNTHIA

SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT:
Eric Sträng is a Data Scientist at Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany, and will provide expertise on **#clinicaldata** in **#hematology**. The involvement of Charité in SYNTHIA focuses on creating **#SyntheticData** that mirrors real clinical data, enabling breakthroughs in **#PersonalizedMedicine** for more effective and tailored **#patient treatments**.

#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #HealthcareInnovation #AIinHealthcare #DataScience #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURsearch

SYNTHIA
@IHI_SYNTHIA

#SYNTHIA is supported by **@IHI_Europe** (IHI JU No 101172872). JU receives support from **@HorizonEU**, **@COCIR**, **@EFPIA**, **@EuropaBio**, **@MedTech Europe**, **@Vaccines Europe**, **@DNV**.

Please help us reach out and share our posts with your network in Europe and beyond! 🙌 - Thank you very much in advance!

#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #SyntheticData #DataGeneration #PrecisionMedicine More info: contact@ihi-synthia.eu
#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #SyntheticData #PrecisionMedicine #health

synthia

Synthetic Data Generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI healthcare applications

Social Media Campaign | General Introduction | Core deck

Last edited | 27 October 2024 | EdW

X / Twitter
LinkedIn

	Content	Image
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LinkedIn	<p>SYNTHIA: #SyntheticData generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and #AI #healthcare applications.</p> <p>Synthetic data, artificially generated to mimic real patient data, present a solution to many of the challenges faced in health research today. These data allow researchers to overcome the limitations of access to high-quality, real-world datasets and address growing concerns about patient privacy. However, questions have lingered about the quality and applicability of synthetic datasets, especially in diverse and complex scenarios. SYNTHIA will address these challenges head-on by developing validated tools and methods for synthetic data generation across various #data types, including laboratory results, clinical notes, #genomics and imaging. By focusing on six specific #diseases we will demonstrate the utility of synthetic data in advancing #personalizedmedicine.</p> <p>"We firmly believe that synthetic data produced by advanced AI holds significant promise for healthcare, particularly in forward-thinking concepts such as digital twins and trial emulation". Holger Fröhlich, Head of AI & Data Science, Fraunhofer - SYNTHIA Co-Chair</p> <p>Funded by: Innovative Health Initiative (IHI) (IHI JU) GA No 101172872. Supported by: the European Commission European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme; COCIR; EFPIA - European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations; EuropaBio - the European Association for Bioindustries; MedTech Europe; Vaccines Europe; DNV.</p> <p>#SyntheticData #DataGeneration #DataScience g#DataInnovation #AIinHealthcare #DigitalHealth #HealthData #EUResearch #EUInnovation #HorizonEU</p>	
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<p>GE HealthCare, SYNTHIA industry lead published a press release about its role in SYNTHIA.</p> <p>Gopal Avinash, PhD, VP, AI Smart Devices of GE HealthCare who also presented at the SYNTHIA Kick-off meeting said: “Leveraging AI and data integration technologies is vital to tackle the rapidly increasing volume of patient data. Yet healthcare data remains complex and requires careful annotation to be used in research and product development. Synthetic data has huge potential to enhance research and product development in healthcare by augmenting available data. Along with GE HealthCare’s AI strategy, synthetic data can help mitigate bias and drifts in algorithms and reduce privacy risks. Synthetic data can also help speed up the development of robust and generalizable AI models in the healthcare domain. We are excited to explore and develop these methods while enhancing standards and guidelines to build safe and effective synthetic data models with our expert collaborators within Synthia.”</p> <p>Read the GE Healthcare press release: https://lnkd.in/ecwBNtv8</p> <p>Many thanks to Amied Shadmaan Edit Galli Annamaria Csizmadia to make this outreach happen.</p> <p>hashtag#Medtech hashtag#SyntheticData hashtag#DataGeneration hashtag#DataScience hashtag#DataInnovation hashtag#AlinHealthcare hashtag#DigitalHealth</p>	
<p>Shout-out to our partners who inform their communities about SYNTHIA with dedicated messages. Please read below the press release published by Fraunhofer SCAI in German. >> Special thanks to Holger Fröhlich and Michael Krapp and the Fraunhofer colleagues <<.</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/eq4gvtKN</p> <p>#KI hashtag#Patientendaten #Zukunft #SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #SyntheticData #DataGeneration #DataScience #DataInnovation #AIHealth #EURResearch #EUInnovation</p>	
<p>#Syntheticdata, artificially generated to mimic real patient data, presents a solution to many of the challenges faced in #health #research today. These data allow researchers to overcome the limitations of access to high-quality, real-world datasets and address growing concerns about patient privacy. Questions have lingered about the quality and applicability of synthetic datasets, especially in diverse and complex scenarios.</p> <p>>>>>></p> <p>SYNTHIA will address these challenges head-on by developing validated tools and methods for #syntheticdatageneration (SDG) across various data types, including laboratory results, clinical notes, genomics and imaging.</p> <p>>>>>></p> <p>Sign up for our newsletter, mail to: contact@ihi-synthia.eu</p> <p>#SyntheticData #DataGeneration #PrecisionMedicine -> funded by Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)</p>	
<p>#Syntheticdata, artificially generated to mimic real patient data, presents a solution to many of the challenges faced in #health #research today. These data allow #researchers to overcome the limitations of access to high-quality, #RWD real-world datasets and address growing concerns about #patients privacy. Questions have lingered about quality & applicability of synthetic datasets, especially in diverse and complex scenarios. SYNTHIA will address these challenges, scan our objectives. #SyntheticData #DataGeneration #PrecisionMedicine @IHIEurope @HorizonEU</p>	

<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>Shout-out to our partners who inform their communities about SYNHTIA with dedicated messages. Please read below the press release published by Fraunhofer SCAI in German. >> Special thanks to Holger Fröhlich and Michael Krapp and the Fraunhofer colleagues <<.</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/eq4gvtKN</p> <p>hashtag#KI hashtag#Patientendaten hashtag#Zukunft hashtag#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData hashtag#SyntheticData hashtag#DataGeneration hashtag#DataScience hashtag#DataInnovation hashtag#AIHealth hashtag#EURResearch hashtag#EUInnovation</p>	
	<p>SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT: [Link] Styliani Christina Fragkouli and the team at CERTH, Greece, [link INAB CERTH] are working on SYNTHIA's technical aspects, from data management to #syntheticdata generation. Listen to her #SYNTHIA message.</p> <p>By generating synthetic data, with a focus on #AI applications, SYNTHIA aims to create impactful solutions for 6 specific use cases, bridging the public and private sector expertise.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #SyntheticData #AlInHealthcare #HealthcareInnovation #DataScience #DigitalHealth #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch</p>	<p>Video file is integrated</p>
	<p>SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT: [Tag] Styliani Christina Fragkouli and the team at CERTH, Greece, [Tag INAB CERTH] are working on SYNTHIA's technical aspects, from data management to #syntheticdata generation. Listen to her #SYNTHIA message.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #SyntheticData #AlInHealthcare #HealthcareInnovation #DataScience #DigitalHealth #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch</p>	<p>Video file is integrated</p>
	<p>#Syntheticdata are a essential piece for warranting data privacy and simultaneously, advancing #PrecisionMedicine, accelerating patients' access to more effective drugs while preserving the sustainability of EU healthcare systems.</p> <p>With a focus on 6 impactful diseases—#lungcancer, #breast cancer, #MMSM (multiple myeloma), #DLBCL (Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma), #Alzheimers, and #Type2diabetes—we will develop, disease-specific SDG solutions. This innovation will support research, deepen disease understanding, and enhance treatment development.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA #SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #SyntheticData #HealthcareInnovation #DataGeneration #DataScience #PublicPrivatePartnership #CollaborativeResearch #PersonalizedMedicine #PersonalizedHealthcare #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch Funded by (tagged IHI)</p>	
	<p>#Syntheticdata are a essential piece for warranting data privacy and simultaneously, advancing #PrecisionMedicine, accelerating patients' access to more effective drugs while preserving the sustainability of EU healthcare systems. With a focus on 6 impactful diseases—#lungcancer, #breast cancer, #MMSM (multiple myeloma), #DLBCL (Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma), #Alzheimers, and #Type2diabetes—we will develop, disease-specific SDG solutions.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA #SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #SyntheticData #HealthcareInnovation #PersonalizedMedicine #PersonalizedHealthcare #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch</p>	

<p>SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT:</p> <p>Eric Strång is a Data Scientist at [Tag] Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany, and will provide expertise on #clinicaldata in #hematology. Listen to his #SYNTHIA message.</p> <p>The involvement of Charité in SYNTHIA focuses on creating #SyntheticData that mirrors real clinical data, enabling breakthroughs in #PersonalizedMedicine for more effective and tailored #patient treatments.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #HealthcareInnovation #AlinHealthcare #DataScience #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch</p> <p>Funded by (Tag IHI)</p>	<p>Video file is integrated</p>
<p>SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT:</p> <p>Eric Strång is a Data Scientist at Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany, and will provide expertise on #clinicaldata in #hematology. The involvement of Charité in SYNTHIA focuses on creating #SyntheticData that mirrors real clinical data, enabling breakthroughs in #PersonalizedMedicine for more effective and tailored #patient treatments.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #HealthcareInnovation #AlinHealthcare #DataScience #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch</p>	<p>Video file is integrated</p>
<p>SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT:</p> <p>[Tag] Mario Aznar, CEO of MATICAL Innovation, Spain, describes #SYNTHIA as a groundbreaking initiative:</p> <p>"SYNTHIA is extremely ambitious; it combines the unique expertise and knowledge from clinicians with technical expertise from different fields, including artificial intelligence #AI, machine learning, federated learning, and #bigdata. The combination of academia and large companies, including big pharma and medtech, is just outstanding."</p> <p>Listen to his SYNTHIA message.</p> <p>MATICAL Innovation provided strategic consultancy and guidance during SYNTHIA's proposal phase, leading to its role as the Project Management Organization and active participation across multiple work packages.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #PublicPrivatePartnership #PPP #InnovateTogether #FutureOfHealthcare #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch</p> <p>Funded by (tagged IHI)</p>	<p>Video file is integrated</p>
<p>SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT:</p> <p>Mario Aznar, CEO, MATICAL Innovation, Spain, describes #SYNTHIA as a groundbreaking initiative. Listen to his SYNTHIA message.</p> <p>MATICAL Innovation provided strategic consultancy and guidance during SYNTHIA's proposal phase, leading to its role as the Project Management Organization and active participation across multiple work packages.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #PublicPrivatePartnership #PPP #InnovateTogether #FutureOfHealthcare #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch</p>	<p>Video file is integrated</p>

<p>👁️ View our #SYNTHIA project structure in the image below—a visual snapshot of our collaborative framework, where diverse teams tackle complex #SyntheticData challenges through carefully designed work packages</p> <p>Each work package unites specialized teams from academia, pharma, medtech, medical research, and healthcare institutions. Together, we’re advancing SDG with the expertise of SDG developers, FAIR data specialists, therapeutic innovators, clinical researchers, legal minds, socio-economic analysts, policy advocates, regulatory advisors, and communication experts.</p> <p>Collaboration at its best, driving innovation in healthcare! #DataInnovation #HealthCollaboration #FutureOfMedicine #SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch</p> <p>Funded by (tagged IHI)</p>	
<p>👁️ View our #SYNTHIA project structure in the image below—a visual snapshot of our collaborative framework, where diverse teams tackle complex #SyntheticData challenges through carefully designed work packages. Together, we’re advancing SDG with the expertise of SDG developers, FAIR data specialists, therapeutic innovators, clinical researchers, legal minds, socio-economic analysts, policy advocates, regulatory advisors, and communication experts.</p> <p>Collaboration at its best, driving innovation in healthcare! #DataInnovation #HealthCollaboration #FutureOfMedicine #SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch [Tagged IHI and Horizon Europe]</p>	
<p>SYNTHIA is a pioneering collaboration of 32 partners from Medtech, Pharma, Academia, Medical Research, and Healthcare institutions -> dedicated to advancing #SyntheticData in healthcare!</p> <p>Please help us reach out and share our posts with your network in Europe and beyond! 🌍 - Thank you very much in advance!</p> <p>#SYNTHIA is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, Europa Bio, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe and DNV. The UK consortium partner, The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) is supported by UKRI Grant No 101172872.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #SyntheticData #DataGeneration #PrecisionMedicine</p>	
<p>#SYNTHIA is supported by @IHI_Europe (IHI JU No 101172872). JU receives support from @HorizonEU, @COCIR, @EFPIA, @Europa Bio, @MedTech Europe, @Vaccines Europe, @DNV.</p> <p>Please help us reach out and share our posts with your network in Europe and beyond! 🌍 - Thank you very much in advance!</p> <p>#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #SyntheticData #DataGeneration #PrecisionMedicine More info: contact@ihi-synthia.eu</p> <p>#SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #SyntheticData #PrecisionMedicine #health</p>	

	<p>SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT: Aleksandar Babic from DNV, Norway, shares his vision for the future of #SyntheticData. "Our wish is basically to transition from synthetic data as hype into synthetic data becoming a reality, becoming a standard tool in the toolbox for researchers. We hope that Europe can be a preferred place to drive this development that will evolve around personalized medicine". DNV is an independent expert in assurance and risk management. Listen to his SYNTHIA message.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA #SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #PublicPrivatePartnership #CollaborativeResearch #HealthData #FutureOfMedicine #AlinHealthcare #DigitalHealth #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch</p>	Video file is integrated
	<p>SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT: Aleksandar Babic, DNV, Norway, shares his vision for the future of #SyntheticData. DNV is an independent expert in assurance and risk management. #SYNTHIA #SYNTHIA_SyntheticData #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #EURResearch</p>	Video file is integrated
	<p>SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT:</p> <p>Jean Louis Raisaro from CHUV, Switzerland, shares his insights in the #SYNTHIA project, the critical role of privacy in #SyntheticData and the future of #PrecisionMedicine:</p> <p>"Although most people think that synthetic data is private because it's synthetic, actually it is not the case. Therefore we need to establish new metrics that can assess the amount of real information that is still captured in the synthetic data to build trust as a data-sharing tool."</p> <p>Listen to his SYNTHIA message.</p> <p>Through SYNTHIA, we are working to develop advanced generative methods that prioritize #DataPrivacy, ensuring synthetic data remains a reliable resource for #DataInnovation in healthcare.</p> <p>#SYNTHIA #SyntheticData #HealthcareInnovation #DigitalHealth #DataScience #AlinHealthcare #PersonalizedMedicine #HealthData #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU #CollaborativeResearch #research #TheFuturesHere</p>	Video file is integrated
	<p>#SYNTHIA PARTNER SPOTLIGHT: Jean Louis Raisaro from CHUV, Switzerland, shares his insights on the critical role of privacy in #SyntheticData and the future of #PrecisionMedicine. Listen to his SYNTHIA message.</p> <p>#SyntheticData #HealthcareInnovation #DigitalHealth #AlinHealthcare #PersonalizedMedicine #HealthData #IHITransformingHealth #HorizonEU</p>	Video file is integrated
	<p>This video campaign will include all recorded video messages, will be expanded with additional content (text, image, video, animations) and will run until June 2025</p>	

Social Media Campaign | Launch

Last edited | 27 September 2024 | EdW

X / Twitter
LinkedIn

Channels	Text	Image
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Twitter	We are thrilled to announce the launch of #SYNTHIA, a pioneering public-private partnership funded by @IHIEurope ! We are set to revolutionize #personalizedmedicine by leveraging cutting-edge #SyntheticData to drive #research > #SYNTHIA_SyntheticData @HorizonEU #DataGeneration	
Twitter	Launching SYNTHIA: Synthetic data generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI healthcare applications. Focus: solid tumors #Lungcancer, #breast cancer, blood cancers Multiple #myeloma #MSM, diffuse large B-cell lymphoma #DLBL #lymphoma #AlzheimersDisease	
LinkedIn	Launching SYNTHIA: Synthetic data generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI healthcare applications. Focus: solid tumors hashtag#Lungcancer, hashtag#breast cancer, blood cancers Multiple hashtag#myeloma hashtag#MMSM, diffuse large B-cell lymphoma hashtag#DLBL, hashtag#Alzheimers, hashtag#Type2Diabetes	
Twitter	Excited to launch SYNTHIA, a collaboration of 32 partners from Medtech, Pharma, Academia, Medical Research, and Healthcare institutions - all dedicated to advancing #SyntheticData in healthcare! Press release: www.ih-synthia.eu #DataGeneration #PrecisionMedicine @IHIEurope @HorizonEU	
LinkedIn	SYNTHIA is a pioneering collaboration of 32 partners from Medtech, Pharma, Academia, Medical Research, and Healthcare institutions - uniting SDG developers, FAIR data experts, clinical researchers, developers of therapies and data-based tools, legal experts, socio-economic analysts, regulatory, policy advocacy, and communication -> all dedicated to advancing hashtag#SyntheticData in healthcare! hashtag#DataGeneration hashtag#PrecisionMedicine -> funded by Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)	
Twitter	Launching SYNTHIA: New pioneering #public-private partnership for a 360° vision on advancing healthcare applications through #SyntheticData use. @IHI_Europe @HorizonEU @IHIEurope @HorizonEU @COCIR @EFPIA @EuropaBio @medtecheurope @VaccinesEurope @DNV_Group.	

<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>SYNTHIA means: hashtag#SyntheticData generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and hashtag#AI hashtag#healthcare applications.</p> <p>SYNTHIA is new pioneering hashtag#public-private partnership for a 360° vision on advancing healthcare applications through SyntheticData use. Its mission: Leverage synthetic data to propel personalized medicine to new heights.</p> <p>Please scan the quote of the SYNTHIA Coordinator Guillermo Sanz, Medical Research Institute La Fe (IIS La Fe) and read more in our press release at www.ih-synthia.eu</p> <p>This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI) Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA - European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations, EuropaBio - the European Association for Bioindustries, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe and DNV.</p>	
<p>Twitter</p>	<p>Launching SYNTHIA -> Collaboration & Innovation: Bringing together the brightest minds to foster trust in #syntheticdata, build a dedicated federated platform, and pave the way for future breakthroughs in healthcare. #FutureOfMedicine #Datascience #EUInnovation #HealthResearch</p>	
<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>SYNTHIA is a new pioneering #public-private partnership for a 360° vision on advancing healthcare applications through SyntheticData use.</p> <p>SYNTHIA means: #SyntheticData generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and #AI #healthcare applications.</p> <p>It's about collaboration and innovation. By bringing together the brightest minds we aim to foster trust in #syntheticdata, build a dedicated federated platform, and pave the way for future breakthroughs in healthcare.</p> <p>Please scan the quote of the SYNTHIA Project Lead Amied Shadmaan, GE HealthCare read more in our press release at www.ih-synthia.eu</p> <p>This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI) (IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA - European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations, EuropaBio - the European Association for Bioindustries, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe and DNV.</p> <p>#FutureOfMedicine #Datascience g#EUInnovation #HealthResearch</p>	
<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>Launching SYNTHIA, a pioneering public-private partnership funded by the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI).</p> <p>The SYNTHIA project, a groundbreaking public-private partnership set to revolutionize the field of personalized medicine by harnessing the power of synthetic data. As the first IHI project to tackle the critical need for privacy-preserving data solutions in healthcare, SYNTHIA aims to propel research and innovation to new heights, ensuring that patients receive the best possible care while safeguarding their personal information.</p> <p>SYNTHIA is a multidisciplinary collaboration of 32 consortium partners - SDG developers, FAIR data experts, clinical researchers, developers of therapies and data-based tools, legal experts, socio-economic analysts, regulatory, policy advocacy, and communication experts - that will provide a 360° vision on how to advance healthcare applications through SD use</p> <p>Synthetic data, which are artificially generated to mimic real patient data, present a solution to many of the challenges faced in health research today. These data allow researchers to overcome the limitations of access to high-quality, real-world datasets and address growing concerns about patient privacy. However, questions have lingered about the quality and applicability of synthetic datasets, especially in diverse and complex scenarios. SYNTHIA is addressing these challenges head-on by developing validated tools and methods for synthetic data generation (SDG) across various data types, including laboratory results, clinical notes, genomics and imaging. By focusing on six specific diseases the project will demonstrate the utility of synthetic data in advancing personalized medicine: Lung cancer, Breast cancer, Multiple myeloma, Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma, Alzheimer's disease and Type 2 diabetes.</p> <p>Read our press release at www.ih-synthia.eu</p> <p>This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe and DNV.</p>	

LinkedIn SYNTHIA! Just launched online and our Kick-off meeting will take place at Medical Research Institute La Fe (IIS La Fe) on 9 & 10 September!

#Syntheticdata generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI #healthcare applications.

Help us share our posts to reach our audiences in #hematology #MMSM #DLBCL | #oncology #lungcancer - #breastcancer | #Alzheimers | #diabetes

SYNTHIA is a pioneering multidisciplinary collaboration of 32 consortium partners – synthetic data generation (SDG) developers, FAIR data experts, clinical researchers, developers of therapies and data-based tools, legal experts, socio-economic analysts, regulatory, policy advocacy, and communication experts - that will provide a 360° vision on how to advance healthcare applications through synthetic data (SD) use.

SYNTHIA will tackle the critical need for privacy-preserving data solutions in healthcare by developing validated tools and methods for SDG across various data types, including laboratory results, clinical notes, genomics and imaging.

SYNTHIA is funded by the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)(IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe, Vaccines Europe and DNV. Supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program and industry leaders such as COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe, Vaccines Europe, and DNV, SYNTHIA is dedicated to advancing synthetic data generation for healthcare applications, ensuring that data-driven innovations can safely and effectively transform patient care.

#EURsearch #EUInnovation #HealthResearch #research #DataGeneration #DataScience #DataInnovation #AlinHealthcare #DigitalHealth #HealthData #PublicPrivatePartnership #PersonalizedMedicine

LinkedIn A big hallo to the world by all SYNTHIA consortium partners, just finishing the 1st day of the Kick-off meeting at Medical Research Institute La Fe (IIS La Fe)

SYNTHIA stands for #Syntheticdata generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and #AI #healthcare applications. A pioneering multidisciplinary collaboration of 32 consortium partners – synthetic data generation (SDG) developers, FAIR data experts, clinical researchers, developers of therapies and data-based tools, legal experts, socio-economic analysts, regulatory, policy advocacy, and communication experts - that will provide a 360° vision on how to advance healthcare applications through synthetic data (SD) use.

SYNTHIA is funded by the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)(IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA - European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations, EuropaBio - the European Association for Bioindustries, MedTech Europe, Vaccines Europe and DNV. Supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program and industry leaders such as COCIR, EFPIA, EuropaBio, MedTech Europe, Vaccines Europe, and DNV, SYNTHIA is dedicated to advancing synthetic data generation for healthcare applications, ensuring that data-driven innovations can safely and effectively transform patient care.

#hematology #MMSM #DLBCL #oncology #lungcancer #breastcancer #Alzheimers #diabetes

#EURsearch #EUInnovation #HealthResearch #DataGeneration #DataScience #DataInnovation #AlinHealthcare #DigitalHealth #HealthData #PublicPrivatePartnership #PersonalizedMedicine

Annex 3 – Example Power Point base deck

See separate PDF for all slides.

synthia Synthetic Data Generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI healthcare applications

A brief introduction

Leverage synthetic data to propel personalized medicine to new heights.

ih innovative health initiative | Co-funded by the European Union | cocin | etpia | EuropaBio | MedTech Europe | Vaccines Europe | GTH

synthia Synthetic Data Generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI healthcare applications

32 Partners
Including 7 med tech and pharmaceutical industries

From
16
European countries

Duration	Budget
60 months	22.4M€

synthia Synthetic Data Generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI healthcare applications

A brief introduction

Leverage synthetic data to propel personalized medicine to new heights.

innovative health initiative | Co-funded by the European Union | COCIR | efpiA | EuropaBio | MedTech Europe | Vaccines Europe | DNV

November 2024

0

Our mission is to leverage synthetic data to propel personalized medicine to new heights.

synthia

1

A pioneering multidisciplinary collaboration of 32 consortium partners that will provide a 360° vision on how to advance healthcare applications through Synthetic Data (SD) use.

We will tackle the critical need for privacy-preserving data solutions in healthcare by developing validated tools and methods for SDG across various data types, including laboratory results, clinical notes, genomics, imaging, and mobile health data.

2

2

Synthetic Data Generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI healthcare applications

32 Partners
Including 7 med tech and pharmaceutical industries

From
16
European countries

Duration Budget
60 months **22.4M€**

3

The Objectives

- Identify requirements for SD with SYNTHIA clinical use cases
- Develop SDG methods, tools & access to RD
- Establish a framework for SD evaluation, ensuring privacy, quality and bias mitigation
- Validation of SD for various use cases
- Provide access to SD & SDG methods
- Build a community through public and private cohesion, strong communication and outreach plan

4

Our Consortium:

Committed to advancing the use of synthetic data in healthcare.

5

synthia

Our 32 Partners

Committed to advancing the use of synthetic data in healthcare.

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Outcome & exploitation

- Define the gold standard for building safe and effective SD in the EU and beyond
- Set the legal, ethical and regulatory framework for accelerating the adoption of SD for various healthcare applications, including regulatory decision-making
- Deliver a clinical-grade SD cohort for SYNTHIA clinical use cases and validate their application in clinical setting
- Make research and results accessible to all healthcare stakeholders worldwide
- Leverage the use of SD for accelerating patients' access to novel drugs, tools and devices, maximizing development of precision medicine while maintaining sustainability of EU healthcare systems

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With synthetic data as a catalyst, we are ready to accelerate discoveries in medicine, making personalized healthcare more accessible and effective for all.

This project is supported by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) under grant agreement No 101172872. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and COCIR, EFPIA, Europa Bio, MedTech Europe, and Vaccines Europe and DNV. The UK consortium partner, The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) is supported by UKRI Grant 10132181.

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- [ihi_synthia](#)
- contact@ihi-synthia.eu

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Consortium Partners

<p>18 Public Academic Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BSC • CERTH • Charité Berlin • CHUV • EMBL-EBI • Erasmus MC • Fraunhofer Institute • IRCCS, Hospital Policlinico Sant' Orsola • IRCCS, Istituto delle Scienze Neurologiche di Bologna • LUMC • Health Research Institute La Fe • Humanitas Cancer Center • HUS, University of Helsinki • University of Bologna • Universidad Politécnica de Madrid • University of Vienna • Vall d'Hebron Institut d'Oncologia • Vall d'Hebron Institut de Recerca 	<p>7 Private Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMS • DNV • Gates Ventures • GE HealthCare • JANSSEN • Novo Nordisk • PFIZER 	<p>7 Other Partners, incl. SMEs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EAPM • i~HD • ITTM • MATICAL • NICE • Patvocates • TRAIN.AI
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Annex 4 – Videos per September 2024

First round of recorded personal messages by SYNTHIA partners.

The videos are embedded in social media posts as part of the SYNTHIA introduction campaign.

This type of content will be implemented in all channels.

[Video content can be viewed at the SYNTHIA YouTube channel, however the Youtube channels as such will not be promoted >](#)

Message by Sharmini Alagaratnam, DNV - SYNTHIA Partner

Message by Michel Van Speybroeck, JANSSEN - SYNTHIA Partner

Message by Eglys González, Patvocates - SYNTHIA Partner

Message by Aleksandar Babic, DNV - SYNTHIA Partner

Amied Shadmaan, GE Healthcare - SYNTHIA Project Leader

Matt Clement, Gates Ventures - SYNTHIA Partner

Message by Holger Fröhlich, Fraunhofer - SYNTHIA Co-Chair

Message by Jean Louis Raisaro, CHUV - SYNTHIA Partner

Janna Slabbekoorn, MATICAL - SYNTHIA Partner

Message by Mario Aznar, MATICAL - SYNTHIA Partner

Message by Cristina Abad Rodríguez, Health Research...

Message by Enrico Giampieri, University of Bologna - SYNTHIA Partner

Message by Manuel de la Guía Solaz, Innovative Health Initiative...

Message by Eric Sträng, Charite Berlin - SYNTHIA Partner

Message by Styliani Christina Fragkouli, CERTH - SYNTHIA Partner

Annex 5 – Example infographics

Visual representation of the SYNTHIA target audiences

Visual representation of the SYNTHIA Use cases and applications

Visual representation of the SYNTHIA Project Structure

Annex 6 – Example quote cards

“Generation of efficient synthetic databases by using artificial intelligence is a unique way to pursue the goals of maintaining data privacy while offering the tools to advance in precision medicine. The SYNTHIA project, a new pioneering public-private partnership, is the first IHI Project to deal with this urgent need. IISLaFe, is proud to coordinate the IHI SYNTHIA project”.

Guillermo Sanz
Scientific Director,
Health Research Institute La Fe, IISLaFe
SYNTHIA Coordinator

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

“As project lead, GEHC is honoured and humbled to be working alongside world-leading experts across clinical and data science domains, both public and private. The program objectives align well to our ambitions to build safe and effective AI technology, whilst ensuring we are maximizing the potential of synthetic data”.

Amied Shadmaan
Director - AI & Clinical Collaborations
GE HealthCare
SYNTHIA Project Lead

Synthetic Data Generation framework
for integrated validation of use cases
and AI healthcare applications

“Synthetic data offers an amazing opportunity to generate evidence for a given drug, therapy or device, as well as comparative evidence between those and the locally relevant standard of care. This new evidence helps to address the uncertainty that would be in the minds of regulators and payers, and ultimately will improve their decision making, leading to more access of those therapies and devices to patients”,

Marco Dibonaventura
Senior Director, Value & Evidence Team
Lead, Hematology & Biosimilars
Pfizer
SYNTHIA Co-Leader

“Fraunhofer is both excited and honored to take on the roles of project co-chair and co-lead for the Alzheimer’s and Type 2 Diabetes use cases in this innovative public-private partnership. We firmly believe that synthetic data produced by advanced AI holds significant promise for healthcare, particularly in forward-thinking concepts such as digital twins and trial emulation”.

Holger Fröhlich
Head of AI & Data Science,
Fraunhofer
SYNTHIA Co-Chair

Annex 7 – Example of a SYNTHIA flyer and SYNTHIA banner

With synthetic data as a catalyst, SYNTHIA is ready to accelerate discoveries in medicine, making personalized healthcare more accessible and effective for all.

SYNTHIA Consortium partners
 BSC, BMS, CEITEB, Charité Berlin, CHAV, DKV, EMBL-EBL, EAPK, ErasmusMC, Fraunhofer, Gates Ventures, GE Healthcare, Humanitas Research Hospital, IIG, Istituto University Hospital, I.I.D., ISLAIFE, Hospital Universitario Politécnico de Fco. RICOSS, Azienda Ospedaliera Universitaria di Bologna, IRCCS Istituto delle Scienze Neurologiche di Bologna, ITM, JANSSEN, LUMC, MIFICAL, NICE, NutsforHealth, Painschool, Pirova, TUM, University of Bologna, University of Vienna, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Vard, Weizmann Institute de Ciencia.

SYNTHIA Coordinator
 IGHM, Medical Innovation, synthia@ighm.it

SYNTHIA Project Leader
 GE Healthcare

synthia
 Synthetic Data Generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI healthcare applications

SYNTHIA is a pioneering multidisciplinary collaboration of 32 consortium partners - synthetic data generation (SDG) developers, FAIR data experts, clinical researchers, developers of therapies and data-based tools, legal experts, socio-economic analysts, regulatory, policy advocacy, and communication experts - that will provide a 360° vision on how to advance healthcare applications through synthetic data (SD) use.

SYNTHIA will tackle the critical need for privacy-preserving data solutions in healthcare by developing validated tools and methods for SDG across various data types, including laboratory results, clinical notes, genomics, imaging, and mobile health data.

Leverage synthetic data to propel personalized medicine to new heights.

ghm SYNTHIA
 hi_synthia
 it_synthia

www.hi-synthia.eu
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The project has received the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI) under grant agreement No 101019725. This has been supported from the European Union's Horizon research and innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska Curie Grant Agreement No 101019725.

IHM | European Commission | g4p | Weizmann Institute | TUM | IIG

synthia
 Synthetic Data Generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI healthcare applications

Leverage synthetic data to propel personalized medicine to new heights

A multidisciplinary public-private partnership of Synthetic Data Generation developers, FAIR data experts, clinical researchers, developers of therapies and data-based tools, legal experts, socio-economic analysts, regulatory, policy advocacy, and communication experts providing a 360° vision on how to advance healthcare applications through SD Use.

Blood cancer Multiple myeloma Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma	Solid tumors Lung cancer Breast cancer
Neurodegenerative disease Alzheimer's disease	Metabolic disease Type 2 diabetes

The project has received the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI) under grant agreement No 101019725. This has been supported from the European Union's Horizon research and innovation programme under Marie Skłodowska Curie Grant Agreement No 101019725.

IHM | European Commission | g4p | Weizmann Institute | TUM | IIG

Annex 8 – Example of the first SYNTHIA Press Release

Valencia, Spain | 5 September 2024

Leverage synthetic data to propel personalized medicine to new heights: Launching SYNTHIA, a pioneering public-private partnership funded by the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)

- SYNTHIA: Synthetic data generation framework for integrated validation of use cases and AI healthcare applications.
- Focus: Solid tumors, blood cancers, neurodegenerative disease, metabolic disease.
- Consortium partners: 32.

The SYNTHIA project, a groundbreaking public-private partnership funded by the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI), is set to revolutionize the field of personalized medicine by harnessing the power of synthetic data. As the first IHI project to tackle the critical need for privacy-preserving data solutions in healthcare, SYNTHIA aims to propel research and innovation to new heights, ensuring that patients receive the best possible care while safeguarding their personal information.

Unlocking new possibilities in health research

Synthetic data, which are artificially generated to mimic real patient data, present a solution to many of the challenges faced in health research today. These data allow researchers to overcome the limitations of access to high-quality, real-world datasets and address growing concerns about patient privacy. However, questions have lingered about the quality and applicability of synthetic datasets, especially in diverse and complex scenarios. SYNTHIA is addressing these challenges head-on by developing validated tools and methods for synthetic data generation (SDG) across various data types, including laboratory results, clinical notes, genomics and imaging. By focusing on six specific diseases the project will demonstrate the utility of synthetic data in advancing personalized medicine:

- Two solid tumors: Lung cancer and breast cancer;
- Two blood cancers: Multiple myeloma, diffuse large B-cell lymphoma;
- Alzheimer's disease;
- Type 2 diabetes.

Fostering trust through innovation

A key component of the SYNTHIA project is its dedicated federated platform, which will serve as a central resource for the research community. This platform will provide synthetic data generation workflows tailored to specific needs, along with robust frameworks to assess data privacy, quality, and applicability. Each dataset will be clearly labelled with its suitability for various research applications, building trust among stakeholders and promoting the responsible use of synthetic data.

Collaborative efforts driving success

The SYNTHIA consortium partners from Medtech, Pharma, Academia, Medical research and Healthcare institutions are committed to advancing the use of synthetic data in healthcare. The project's outputs will be made accessible to researchers worldwide, fostering a collaborative environment where innovation can thrive.

"In the era of precision medicine, with drugs targeting specific gene mutations, new tools are required to deal with patient's data privacy. Whole genome sequencing, digital imaging, and electronic health record data are the ID of any individual person. All of them are required to be able to provide the patient with the best available treatment. Nevertheless, personal data privacy is a must. Generation of efficient synthetic databases by using artificial intelligence is the unique way to pursue the goals of maintaining data privacy while offering the tools to advance in precision medicine. The SYNTHIA project, a new pioneering public-private partnership, is the first IHI Project to deal with this urgent need. SYNTHIA envisions to generate databases that could be used by the European Medicines Agency to authorize the design of new single arm clinical trials to be used for the approval of more efficient new drugs. That will undoubtedly accelerate patients' access to them and, in return, reduce the cost of those therapies. That is the aim SYNTHIA is committed to for the benefit of the EU society. The Health Research Institute La Fe, IISLaFe, is proud to coordinate the IHI SYNTHIA project". – **Guillermo Sanz, Scientific Director, IISLaFe** - SYNTHIA Academic Lead.

“Leveraging AI and data integration technologies is vital to tackle the rapidly increasing volume of patient data. Yet healthcare data remains complex and requires careful annotation to be used in research and product development. Synthetic data has huge potential to enhance research and product development in healthcare by augmenting available data. Along with GE HealthCare’s AI strategy, synthetic data can help mitigate bias and drifts in algorithms and reduce privacy risks. Synthetic data can also help speed up the development of robust and generalizable AI models in the healthcare industry. We are excited to explore and develop these methods while enhancing data standards and guidelines to build safe and effective synthetic data-based models with our expert collaborators within SYNTHIA,” – **Gopal Avinash, PhD, VP, AI Smart Devices, GE HealthCare** - SYNTHIA Industry Lead

SYNTHIA is a multidisciplinary collaboration of 32 consortium partners - SDG developers, FAIR data experts, clinical researchers, developers of therapies and data-based tools, legal experts, socio-economic analysts, regulatory, policy advocacy, and communication experts - that will provide a 360° vision on how to advance healthcare applications through SD use. SYNTHIA invites researchers, healthcare providers, and innovators to join in pioneering a new era of healthcare research. With synthetic data as a catalyst, SYNTHIA is ready to accelerate discoveries in medicine, making personalized healthcare more accessible and effective for all.

For more information contact SYNTHIA Communications: P.B. [Ellen] de Waal | contact@ihi-synthia.eu

www.ihi-synthia.eu | X: [>](https://twitter.com/IHI_SYNTHIA) | LinkedIn: [>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/ihi-synthia) | YouTube: [>](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCihsynthia)

Annex 9 – Example of the SYNTHIA SharePoint edition 1.0

The SYNTHIA SharePoint is offered to all official partner contacts. A login is required.

